

IMPORTANT POSSIBILITIES FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE TOURISM SECTOR OF THE PROCESS OF COUNTRY

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Annotation. This thesis highlights the evolution of the development of digital technologies and the importance of the digitization process in the development of tourism. There is a classification of digital technologies used in the automation of tourist services.

Keywords: innovation, digital service, tourism, classification, artificial intelligence, marketing

Introduction. The concept of digitization is explained in the scientific literature as the process of converting analog data into machine-readable data using digital technologies available. The development of digital technology began in 1945 with the advent of ¹data storage and processing machines with the end of World War II . By the 1950s, the invention of magnetic memory storage equipment further reduced data storage costs. In the 1960s and 1970s, the first Internet network in the United States, DARPA, was created, which made it possible to send text messages from one computer to another ². In the 1980s, it was possible to communicate with foreign computers using the TCP (transmission control protocol) protocol through this DARPA network. The privatization of digital technology in the United States

¹ Ceruzzi , PE (2003). A History of Modern Computing, Second edition. MIT Press.

² Hafner , K. and M. Lyon (1996). where wizards stay up late. Simon and Schuster Paperbacks.

took place between 1990 and 1995, and by the 2000s the Internet had reached almost every country in the world³.

The digitalization process is creating great opportunities for the development of small tourism entities. For example, today small tourism entities have the opportunity to use processes such as entering new tourism markets, creating new types of business models, cooperating with other enterprises due to digital technologies. The use of digital technologies in tourism has become especially popular due to the coronavirus pandemic that occurred in 2020⁴. The following digital technologies play an important role in the development of tourism:

1. Mobile and cloud technologies. In the organization of trips for tourists, services such as mobile payments, online booking are carried out via mobile internet. Tourist entities Cloud technologies also allow for remote business management.

2. Data analysis. Tourism entities now have a large database of consumer behavior through websites, messengers and other digital platforms. Therefore, tourism entities feel the need for professionals who know how to analyze big data for themselves.

3. Artificial intelligence. Used in the automation of tourist services. This technology allows for service without human intervention (e.g., call center).

4. Internet of Things (IoT). This technology is used in the organization of smart tourism, where sensors are connected to a single network that allows you to monitor in real time the behavior of tourists, the state of the environment, the efficient use of resources, and so on.

5. Virtual reality. Virtual reality real objects 3 D allows tourists to model the real world by moving to virtual objects. At the same time, tourists will have the

³Greenstein, D. (2000). Building and delivering the virtual world: Commercializing services for internet access. *The Journal of Industrial Economics* 48, 391–411.

⁴ Q.J.Mirzaev, E.Sh.Shavqiev, B.K.Janzakov. *Innovative Economy: Textbook*. - T .: “Innovative Development Publishing House”, 2020. Pages 153-156

opportunity to make a virtual visit to the destination from a distance, away from home.

6. Blockchain. Today, evolving "smart" contracts, payment systems and other users' personal information are being exchanged through blockchain technology.

Users of social networks are growing rapidly all over the world, and these networks are constantly evolving. Currently, the most popular platforms in our country are Facebook, Youtube, Pinterest and Twitter (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Dynamics of the social network market in Uzbekistan in 2021⁵

In general, it is no exaggeration to say that the development of the social network market is leading to the acceleration and development of globalization processes. It is social networks that play a key role in the spread of the concept of the digital economy and its relevance today ⁶. In our country, not only social networks, but also other areas of ICT are developing.

In addition, the growth of average wages in the ICT sector is accompanied by an increase in enterprises with foreign capital. Wage growth is due to the high staff deficit in the industry and the growing workload of service enterprises in this area. This is due to the fact that the process of globalization is intensifying all over the

⁵ <https://gs.statcounter.com/social-media-stats> author's development based on site information

⁶ B.Janzakov . The innovative development of tourism and other theoretical frameworks of competitiveness. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology. Vol. 29. No. 5, 2020, pp. 1774-1780

world, the opportunity to stand in one corner of the world and serve a person in another corner, in general, the service has reached a global level.

The development of digital services and the digital economy is reflected not only in programming, computers and public services, but also in the implementation of projects such as the "smart city".

In our opinion, special attention should be paid to the automation of labor productivity in the tourism sector:

- Features of tourism services: level of communication with people, criteria of service quality, resource consumption, etc .;

- Qualification level of employees of tourist subjects, level of access to digital technologies;

- Development of ICT infrastructure, internet speed, availability of electricity and other energy sources.

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